

AYURVEDIC CONCEPTS AND MANAGEMENT OF HYPOTHYROIDISM: A REVIEW ARTICLE

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ABSTRACT

Hypothyroidism is one of the most prevalent endocrine disorders worldwide and results from inadequate synthesis of thyroid hormones. The thyroid gland secretes thyroxine (T₄) and triiodothyronine (T₃), which play a vital role in regulating metabolism, growth, and development. Elevated thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) levels are considered a primary indicator of hypothyroidism. Sedentary lifestyle and unhealthy dietary habits contribute significantly to thyroid dysfunction. From an Ayurvedic perspective, hypothyroidism is understood as a disorder involving *Agnimandya* (impaired digestive fire) and imbalance of *Doshas*. Predominantly, *Kapha* and *Vata Doshas* are aggravated, while *Pitta Dosh* is reduced, leading to systemic manifestations. The condition is also associated with vitiation of *Rasa Dhatu* and involvement of multiple *Srotas*. Although hypothyroidism is not described directly in classical Ayurvedic texts, it can be correlated with *Anukta*

Vyadhi. This review highlights the Ayurvedic conceptual understanding and management principles of hypothyroidism.

KEYWORDS: Hypothyroidism, *Agni*, *Dosha*, *Dushya*, *Srotas*, *Anukta Vyadhis*.

INTRODUCTION

In Today's scenario, due to the sedentary lifestyle and stress alternations in the activities of the neuroendocrine system cause newer health challenges such as hormonal imbalance, which

leads to a disorder such as Hypothyroidism.^[1] The incidence of thyroid disorder in India is high, with hypothyroidism being a condition that is not adequately controlled in the country at the present.^[2] The thyroid gland is an important sensitive endocrine gland. The major function of thyroid gland is to control the rate of metabolism.^[3] Lack of thyroid hormone with respect to metabolic demand results in disorder called Hypothyroidism. Thyroid hormone is required for the normal functioning of each and every tissue of the body. Hence, its deficiency manifests as multisystem involvement.^[4]

Hypothyroidism is a commonly prevailing disorder in adult Indian population. It is estimated that about 42 million people suffer from thyroid disorder in India, of which hypothyroidism is most common with a prevalence of 5.4%.⁴ Prevalence of hypothyroidism is found to be high affecting approximately one in 10 adults according to Indian journal of endocrinology and metabolism year 2013. Women are 6 times more prone than men. Older overweight females seem to be more prone than men.^[5]

Thyroid gland is a tiny, butterfly-shaped gland located right below Adam's apple at the base of the front of the neck. The thyroid gland is an endocrine gland that is found in the lower front and sides of the neck. The thyroid gland generates hormones that control heart, muscular, and digestive function, as well as brain development and maintenance. Hypothyroidism, hyperthyroidism, goitre, Hashimoto's thyroiditis and thyroid cancer are all common thyroid problems, Hypothyroidism is the most frequent of these disorders.

The thyroid gland is made up of several spherical follicular cells. Tri-iodothyronin (T3) and Tetra iodothyronin (Thyroxine) (T4) are secreted by follicular cells. Parafollicular cells, which secrete calcitonin, are found between follicular cells. T3 and T4 are Iodine-containing tyrosine derivatives.^[6] The thyroid hormones, tri iodothyronine and Tetra iodothyroxine, have a huge impact on human health, affecting every part of our metabolism. Hypothyroidism is a disorder in which the thyroid gland produces insufficient thyroid hormone, causing problems with heart rate, body temperature and other elements of metabolism. It is more common in older women.

Hypothyroidism is not directly mentioned in *Samhitas*. Many ailments are not directly mentioned in ayurvedic scriptures, but their treatment is adequately documented in them. "It is not required for *Vaidya* to know the name of the disease before commencing the treatment," according to *Madhavnidaan*, "but *Vaidya* should cure the patient on the basis of

examination of *Prakruti* (physical and mental constitution), *Vikruti* (pathology), *Saartaa* (elemental tissues and mind), *Sahanan* (compactness of the body), *Pramaan* (quantity), *Saatmya* (compatible), *Satva* (mental status), *Aahaar Shakti* (digestive power), *Vyaayaam Shakti* (capacity of doing physical work), *Vaya* (age) *Adhisthaan* (location), *Bheda*, (types) and *Hetu* (cause), *Shata-kriya-kala* (the stage of a sickness) should also be elicited to determine the curability of the disease and thus accordingly patient should be treated.^[7]

According to Ayurveda, impairment of functions of *Agni* is the prime cause of hypothyroidism. Hypofunctioning of the *Jatharagni* (digestive power) affects the *Dhatavagni* (digestive power of tissue) and *Medogni*, (digestive power of adipose tissue) resulting in a pathological cascade. Ayurvedic medicines and *Panchakrma* (five purification procedures) treatments, such as *Vamana* (induced vomiting) and *Virechana*, (induced purgation) are employed because they are relatively effective and have little negative effects.^[8] This review aims to discuss both Ayurvedic medicine concept of hypothyroidism pathophysiology, line of treatment and future areas of research based on use of herbal plants or dietary supplements.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study is carried out by literature search and data is reviewed critically. The clinical presentation of hypothyroidism was studied from modern pathology textbooks and by searching various online medical research databases like Google Scholar, Pubmed, Ayucare and other national research databases. This study is done by literature search and critical review of the obtained facts. Literature search has been done by manually searching Ayurvedic texts or *Samhitas* The study of various Ayurvedic texts were made critically and an effort is made to understand the complete pathogenesis of Hypothyroidism in terms of *Dosha*, *Dushya*, *Agni* and *Srotas*. This review is carried out with an aim to understand the disease Hypothyroidism in Ayurvedic principles and to establish the management protocol through Ayurveda.

Etiology/ Nidana

Hypothyroidism is classified into,

1. Primary hypothyroidism: It is due to inadequate function of the thyroid gland itself. Most common causes of Primary hypothyroidism are iodine deficiency, autoimmune thyroid disease, Congenital, drugs and iatrogenic causes.
2. Secondary hypothyroidism: It is due to not getting enough stimulation by thyroid stimulating hormones.

Pathogenesis/Samprapti

Primary Hypothyroidism results from two mechanisms.

1. Deficiency of Thyroid Hormones caused by destruction of thyroid follicles, as in Hashimoto's thyroiditis (Autoimmune disorder).^[9]
2. Resistance of peripheral tissues to thyroid hormones.

In Ayurveda, we can consider these two pathologies in the following way.

1. *Dhatukshaya Janya (Beejadoshha Janita)*

Due to *Apathya Nidan Sevana* and also *Bijadusha*, there is *Tridosha Dushti* leading to *Jatharagni Mandya* which causes *Dhatwagnimandya*, leading to *Uttarrottara Dhatu Vikriti*, ultimately causing *Oja Vikriti*. This *Vikrita Ojas* (in this case it is often caused by the presence of *Pitta Dosha*) affects the *Vyadhi Kshamatva* of the body, attacking the thyroid gland and the autoimmune condition develops. Thus, it is a *Kaphapitta Samsarga* condition.^[10]

2. *Avarana Janya*

Thyroid hormone functions are similar to the functions of *Agni (Jatharagni, Dhatwagni and Bhootagni)* in our body causing transformations /tissue metabolism at various levels and thus maintaining the BMR. *Agnimandya* at any level due to *Kaphakara Nidana* results in increased *Dhatugata Mala Sanchaya*, resulting in *Srotorodha* causing compromised *Dhatu Saras* leading to both physical and mental features in hypothyroidism. *Vata* acts as a *Yogavah* in aggravating the *Kapha Dushti*. Thus, it is a *Vata-Kapha Samsarga* condition.^[10]

Samprapti Ghatakas

1. *Dosha: Vata*- Primarily *Vyana, Samana, Udana*
Pitta- Primarily *Pachak, Sadhaka, Ranjaka*
Kapha- Primarily *Kledaka, Sleshaka, Tarpaka*
2. *Dhatu*: all seven but specifically *Rasa, Rakta, Meda, Mamsa, Asthi, Shukra*
3. *Srotasa: Anna, Udaka, Rasa, Rakta, Mamsa, Meda*
4. *Agni: Dhatvagni* esp. *Rasa, Rakta, Medovaha, Bhutagni*
5. *Aam*: Usually Present
6. *Updhatu: Raja* and *Snayu*
7. *Rogamarga-Bahya, Abhyantara, Madhyama*
8. *Gunas*: Vitiation *Snigdha, Manda, Picchila, Guru, Ruksha* and *Sheeta*

Clinical Presentation/Roopa

As discussed above, Hypothyroidism results in slowing down of the metabolic process. It usually results in a number of clinical signs and symptoms. The severity of the signs and symptoms depends on the degree of thyroid dysfunction and the time course of development of the disease. The symptoms of hypothyroid are very nonspecific. So, the common presentation of hypothyroidism along with Ayurvedic prospective are tabulated below.

Table No. 1: Clinical presentation of hypothyroidism according to Dosha Srotas involvement.

Clinical presentation ^[11]	Dosha involved ^[12]	Srotas ^[13,14]
Fatigue, loss of energy	Vata, Kapha	Rasavaha
Dry Skin	Vata	Rasavaha
Decreased vision, decreased hearing	Vata	Rasavaha
Increased sensitivity to cold	Vata, Kapha	Rasavaha
Paraesthesia, Nerve entrapment syndrome	Vata	Rasavaha, Medovaha, Majjavaha
Muscle pain, joint pain	Vata	Mansavaha, Asthivaha
Hair loss, coarse, brittle, straw like hair	Vata	Asthivaha
Dull facial expression, depression, mental impairment, forgetfulness, inability to concentrate	Vata	Manovaha
Constipation	Vata	Purishvaha
Menstrual disturbance, impaired fertility.	Vata	Rasavaha, Artavavaha, Shukravaha
Hoarseness of voice	Vata, Kapha	Pranavaha
Weight gain	Kapha	Rasavaha, Medovaha
Decreased appetite	Kapha	Annavaha, Rasavaha
Periorbital puffiness	Kapha	Rasavaha
Abdominal distension, non-pitting edema	Kapha	Rasavaha

Anukta Vyadhi

Acharyas had vision of forthcoming new diseases; hence they explained the concept of understanding the new diseases Anukta Vyaadhi. Anukta Vyaadhis are the diseases which are neither elaborated or nor described in lexicons of Ayurveda. Such concepts used to describe, understand, adopt and extend new things, such as identification of new Hetu, Linga and Aushadha based on existing principles of Ayurveda.^[15] To understand and appreciate the concept of Anukta Vyadhi, it is essential to consider basic concepts of Ayurveda viz, Dosha Dhatu Mala Vijnana, Agni, Srotas, Ojus and Manas. Understanding the Rasapanchaka of Ahaara Dravyas, is also helpful to know its effects on above factors which are responsible for the manifestation of disease.

Though *Anukta Vyadhis* are not interpreted by their names, the cluster of signs and symptoms and the underlying pathology can be understood by the basic principles stated above which not only helpful in understanding the pathogenesis but also gives direction to think in terms of treatment for the same. Due to innumerable diseases, the one who cannot label a disorder with some name should not feel ashamed because all disorders have no established footing by name. As disease cannot occur without involvement of *Doshas*, hence even if the disease is not specifically mentioned, the intelligent clinician should treat the disease as manifested by the signs and symptoms of vitiated *Doshas*. Hypothyroidism is one among them, which is new disease also included in lifestyle disorders, which didn't possess any Ayurvedic name and not found directly in Ayurvedic texts. Hence the signs and symptoms of this disease is to be understood first based on the contemporary science. By observing *Doshas*, *Srotas* involved, *Samprapti*.

Review Regarding Correlation Of Hypothyroidism With Other Different Conditions in Ayurveda

In ayurvedic classics the term *Galaganda*^[16] is mentioned for visible neck swelling. Some scholars try to correlate hypothyroidism with *Ras dhatudushti* or *Kapha dosh dushti* or *Galganda*. In the pathological condition when the enlargement of thyroid gland occurs is visualized superficially, in this condition Acharya described it and gave the title *Galaganda*. This type of swelling is seen in case of Hyperthyroidism and long standing untreated hypothyroidism. Hence the treatment mentioned in *Galaganda* can be useful in treating hypothyroidism in early stages.

The earliest description of neck swelling is found in *Atharvaveda* by the name *Apachi*.^[17] Literary review predicts the correlation of *Galaganda* with goiter or some tumor pathology where thyroid functions may or may not be affected.

The clinical scenario of hypothyroidism presents with various constitutional symptoms of *Rasa dushti* or *Kapha dushti* rather than restricting to just a localized pathology. Hence it is better not to restrict hypothyroidism with *Galaganda* alone.

Kaphavritta Udana Vata, *Kaphavritta Samana Vata*, *Kaphaja Pandu*, *Kaphaja Grahani*, *Bahudoshavastha* and *Sannipata* etc. are the conditions having resemblance with hypothyroidism. *Srotoshodhana*, *Agnideepana* and *Vatanulomana* are the main principles to be achieved.

From the above mentioned tables it is clear that in hypothyroidism there is abnormality of *Jatharagni* and *Dhatwagni* along with abnormality of *Kapha* and *Vata Dosha* as well as *Rasavaha*, *Raktavaha*, *Medovaha*, *Sukravaha* and *Manovaha Srotas*.

Disease Management

Concept for the pathogenesis of disease are different in Ayurveda and modern therapeutic system. Accordingly the way of treatment also change, but ultimate goal is to overcome to diseased condition.

Modern therapeutic prospective

The treatment as per the modern medicine practice include use of Levothyroxine sodium as a part of hormone replacement therapy (available as Synthroid, Eltroxin), thyroid extract preparation, and antioxidants such as selenium.

Levothyroxine Therapy

Levothyroxine (T4) is the standard replacement therapy in primary or central hypothyroidism.^[18] Many physiological and pathological conditions can impair levothyroxine absorption such as patients factors (compliance), certain foods (e.g. grapes, coffee, etc.), drugs (e.g. antacids, sucralfate etc.) gastrointestinal diseases (e.g. H. pylori infection). Certain new formulations are introduced for patient with impaired absorption of Levothyroxine i.e. Liquid formulation (patented by Institute Biochimique SA (IBSA), Lugano, Switzerland) and soft gel formulation with improved bioavailability over traditional tablets.^[19] Pharmacodynamic equivalence of T4 and L-triiodothyronine (T3) combination is believed to be approximately 1:3.^[20] Hypo-thyroidism, in an adult can be treated by administering sustained-release formulation of T3 (0.005-0.03 µg/kg body weight/hour/day) in 5-25 µg dose at daily basis, without the need of administering the therapeutic dose of T4.^[21]

Ayurvedic Principle of Management (*Chikitsa*)

On the basis of above discussion, the line of treatment with specific target to *Agni* along with *Dhatwagni*, *Rasavaha*, *Mamsavaha*, *Medovaha*, *Manovaha Srotas* as well as *Tridosha* specifically *Vata* and *Kapha Dosha* should be administered in Hypothyroidism.

1. *Nidan Parivarjana*
2. *Shamana: Vata Kapha Dosha Shamana*
3. *Agni Deepan, Langhana* at the beginning and repeatedly.
4. *Dhatugatha Malapachana*

5. *Shodhana: Strotoshodhana*

6. *Rasayana*

7. *Yogasana*

1. *Nidan Parivarjana*: This means avoidance of the various causative factors of the disease. It is the first line of treatment of any disease. Hypothyroidism manifests as a result of *Kapha-Vatavridhi*, *Agnimandya* formation of *Amadosha* and *Rasa Dhatudushti*.

2. *Langhana*: Plays an important role in the management of hypothyroidism, as the condition is primarily associated with *Kapha Dosha* aggravation and *Agnimandya* (diminished digestive and metabolic fire). Hypothyroidism manifests with heaviness, lethargy, weight gain, and cold intolerance features indicative of *Kapha* dominance. *Langhana* helps to reduce excess *Kapha*, stimulate *Agni*, and improve metabolic activity. Thus, *Langhana* forms a fundamental principle in the Ayurvedic management of hypothyroidism.

3. *Shamana, Agni Deepan, Dhatugatha Malapachana*

a) Single Herbs

Table No. 2: Herbal Plants with thyrotropic activities. [22,23,24,25]

Sr.No	Botanical Name	Common names	Part used	Actions
1	<i>Bacopa monnieri</i>	<i>Brahmi</i>	Whole plant	It raised both 13 & 14, reduce oxidative stress, improves memory, concentration
2	<i>Withania somnifera</i>	<i>Ashwagandha</i>	Root	It lowered cortisol, raise thyroid hormones levels, lowers oxidative stress.
3	<i>Commiphora mukul</i>	<i>Guggulu</i>	Oleo-resin, gum	It improved thyroid histology, raised T3, T4 ratio.
4	<i>Moringa oleifera</i>	<i>Shigru</i>	Root, seeds, leaf	Used in hypothyroidism to normalize hormone level.
5	<i>Bauhinia variegata</i>	<i>Kanchanara</i>	Bark	It reduced swelling of neck, increased serum thyroid hormone concentrations, decreased Cholesterol and improved thyroid histology.
6	<i>Inula racemosa</i>	<i>Pushkarmool</i>	Root	It stimulated thyroid histology.
7	<i>Crataeva nurvula</i>	<i>Varuna</i>	Bark, Root	It possessed antitumour activity for extragrowths of thyroid.
8	<i>Pistia startiodes</i>	<i>Jalakumbhi</i>	Whole plant	It reduced swelling of thyroid.
9	<i>Vitex nigundo</i>	<i>Nirgundi</i>	Root, leaves, seeds	It reduced swelling of thyroid.
10	<i>Linum usitatissimum</i>	<i>Alsi/Bijari</i>	Seeds	It maintain thyroid health, boost production of thyroid hormones.
11	<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	<i>Adrak</i>	Rhizome	It restored thyroid health in hypothyroidism.
12	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	<i>Aaragvatha</i>	Root, leaves,	It raise thyroid hormone levels, decreased

			flower, fruit pulp	cholesterol.
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b) Polyherbal drugs

Triphala: It is one of the most popular herbal remedies which cleanse by promoting bowel movement. It is having *Deepana, Pachana, Vatanulomana* and *Srotoshodhana* properties. Hence it helps digestion and assimilation. It significantly reduces serum cholesterol and lipid levels (as hypercholesterolemia occurs due to Hypothyroidism).^[26]

Trikatu: *Trikatu* is having *Katu Rasa, Katu Vipaka* and *Ushana Virya, Ushna, Tikshna, Laghu, Rukksha Guna* therefore it having properties like *Deepan, Pachana* and *Srotoshodhana* along with it pacify the *Kapha-Vata*. It is commonly used to treat the condition of *Mandagni* and *Aamdosha* hence effective in correcting the dysfunction of *Agni* seen in Hypothyroidism.^[27]

Panchkola: It comprises of five drugs i.e., *Pippali, Pippalimula, Chavya, Chitraka* and *Sunthi*. *Panchkola* is predominantly having *Ushna, Tikshna, Laghu, Ruksha, Katu Rasa* and *Vipaka, Ushna Virya*. *Panchkola* is considered as one of the excellent drugs to treat the condition of *Mandagni* along with *Aamdosha* and *Kapha-Vata* disorders.^[27]

Dhatwagni Deepana

Shaddharanam Choornam (Bhaishajya-ratnavali Vatavyadhiadhikara 26: 9-10, Bhaishajyaratnavali Urustambachikitsa 28, Sushruta samhita Vatavyadhichikitsa)

Panchakola Choorna (Sharangdhara Samhita Madhyama Khanda 6: 13-14)

Vaishwanara Choorna (Chakradtta Amavata Chikitsa)

Indukanta Ghrita (Sahasra Yoga Ghritaprakarana 5)

Dhatugatha Mala Pachana

Pachanamrutam Kwatha (Sahasrayoga Kashayaprakarana 39)

Guggulutiktaka Kwatha (Ashtangahrudayam Chiktisasthana 21/57-60)

Guduchyadi Kwatha (Sharangdhara Samhita Madhyamakhandanda 2/8)

Gorakhmundi Swarasa (Sharangdhara Samhita Madhyamakhandanda, Swarasa/16)

Chitrakadi Kashaya (Sushrutha Chikitsa 14/4)

Shiva Gulika (Ashtanga Hrudaya Uttarasthana 49/293)

Vata Kapha Shamana-Doshapratyanikachikitsa

Ashtavarga Kwatha (Sahasrayoga Vatarogachikitsa.)

Navaka Guggulu (Bhaishajya Ratnavali Medoroga Chikitsa 39/43)

Punarnavadi Kwatha (Bhaishajya Ratnavali Udararoga 43-44),

Asanadi Kwatha (Astangahradayam Sutrastana 15/20)

Guggulu Tiktaka Ghrita (Ashtangahrudayam Chiktisasthana 21/57-60)

Yogas like^[3]***Kashya kalpana***

1. *Varunadi kashyam Asanadi Kashayam*

2. *Vatsakadi Kashayam*

3. *Guggulutiktaka Kashyam*

4. *Hamsapathyadi Kashyam*

Churna Kalpana

1. *Shaddharana Churna*

2. *Shadushan Churna*

3. *Chopchinyadi Churna*

4. *Vyoshadi Churna*

5. *Guggulu panchapalam Churna*

6. *Abhaya Churna*

Vati Kalpana

1. *Kanchanara Guggulu*

2. *Triphala Guggulu*

3. *Vyoshadya Guggulu*

Arishta Kalpana

1. *Amrta Arishtam*

2. *Abhayarishtam*

3. *Ayaskriti*

Rasaoushadi

1. *Mandura Bhasma*

2. *Swarna Bhasma*

3. *Abraka Bhasma*

Lepas

1. *Nichuladi Lepa*

2. *Devadaru vishala Lepa*

3. *Hastikarna Palasha Lepa*

4. *Sarshapadi Pralepa*

4. Shodhana

Vamana- For *Kapha Chedana* and removing *Avarana* according to *Bala* of *Rugna* and disease condition. *Vamana (Kapha Chedana) Madana Pippali, Vacha, Yashtimadhu, Saindhava*, honey.

Virechana- It maintains *Pitta- Rakta Shuddhi*. It brings *Vatanulomana* and *Srotoshudhi. Mishraka Sneha*.

Nasya- It is good to eliminate *Sanchita Mala* from *Uthamanga* in Hypothyroidism. It brings *Indriyabala* and *Manobala. Nasya Shadbindu Taila (Bheshaj Ratnavali Shirorogadhikara 49-51), Anu taila*.

5. Rasayana^[28]: *Rasayana* are to be given after *Samyak Shodhana* in Hypothyroidism. *Rasayana* work at *Dhatwagni* Level correcting *Dhatwagni Mandya* which are seen in Hypothyroidism. e.g *Shilajatu, Pipali, Chitrakam*.

6. Yogasan: The *Yogasanas* like *Halasanam* (plough pose), *Paschimothanasanam* (plough pose), *Matysaasanam* (fish pose), *Sarvangasanam* (plough pose), *Pavanamukta Sanam* (seated forward bend pose), *Sirshasana* (head low pose), *Suptavajrasana, Suryanamaskaram* (sun salutations), *Simhagarjanasanam* (loin pose), and *Kandarasanam* are found beneficial, The breathing exercises like *Pranayamam-Sheetali, Seethkara, Sadanda, Bastrika, Anulomaviloma Pranayam* and *Ujjayi Pranayam Swasa* aids the healthy functioning of thyroid gland.^[29]

Pathya

Aharaj Pathya: *Ruksha Katu Dravya* (dry and bitter substance) *Deepana Dravya*(substances which increases appetite) and drugs like *Guggulu* and *Shilajatu* are *Pathya. Purana Ghritapana, Jeerna Lohita Shali, Yava, (barley) Mudga, (green gram), Patola* (pointed

gourd), *Rakta Shigru*(drumstick), *Kathillaka (Punarnava)*, *Salincasaka*, *Vetagra*, *Rohit Matsya (Rohu fish)*, *Saindhaiva* salt, cow's ghee (butter) and milk, *Raktashali* (red rice).^[30]

Viharaj Pathya: It specifies the physical activities as well as the daily routine to be followed. *Dincharya* (daily regimen), *Rutucharya* (seasonal regimen), *Nidra* (sleep) *Dhaarneeya Vega*, (which should be controlled) and *AdhaarneeyaVega* (which should not be controlled) are all Ayurvedic scriptures that, when followed, help to improve personal and social cleanliness, ultimately increasing the quality of life and preserving a healthy and disease-free life.^[31]

Maanasika Pathya: *Manasika Pathya* means maintaining a healthy state of mind. Even though a person is physically well, he cannot be entirely healthy until his mental health is in good shape. To minimize psychological disturbances and sustain *Indriyabhigraha* (control over sense organs), *Acharyas* have defined various concepts such as *Achararasayana* (following ethics and values), *Sadvritta*, *Sadachara*, and meditation practice (sensory and motor perceptions and control)and *Svasyanigraha* (self control) restrain from *Chinta* (worrying), *Vichara* (thinking), *Krodha* (anger), *Shoka* (grief) etc. Following these helps to lead a stress free life which is a major cause for all kinds of morbidity especially in hypothyroidism.^[32]

Apathya

Aharaj apathya: *Viruddha Ahar* (incompatible diet) is main cause of hypothyroidism. It include *KshiraVikruti* (milk products), *IkshuVikruti* (products from sugar cane), all types of *Mamsa Ahar* (meat), *Anupa Mamsa*, *Pishtaannam*, *Madhura* (sweet), *Amla Rasa* (sour) and *Guru Ab -hishyandakari Dravya* (substance which are causes obstructions in channels). *Yavaka* (Barley), drinking river water in rainy season, mustard, *Cilicima* fish, ghee and milk of sheep, *Kusumbha Taila*, *Kumbhira*, *Cataka*, *Nikucha* (artocarpus), *Phanita*.^[33]

Viharaj apathya: As per *Ritu*, *Viharaja Apathyas* such *Diwaswapna* (day sleeping) *Ratri Jaagarana* (night awakening), *Vegadharan* (suppression of natural urge) and *Pragnaparadaha*(self-made faults) are specifically listed as causative factors for flawed and unhealthy lifestyles leading thyroid gland dysfunctions.

OBSERVATION AND DISCUSSION

In most of the cases hypothyroidism, a specific cause is not apparent. It is believed that hypothyroidism is usually secondary to an autoimmune reaction.^[34] In autoimmune disorders,

the immune system cells do not recognize the cell as "self" and mount an immune response against them. This self-attack by the immune system increases inflammation and inflammation has a profound effect on all aspects of thyroid metabolism and physiology. Pro-inflammatory cytokines can inhibit type 2 5'-deiodinase enzyme activity which is required for the conversion of T4 to T3.^[35] Thyroid hormones stimulate diverse metabolic activities in most tissues, leading to an increase in basal metabolic rate. By way of analogy, the action of thyroid hormones is akin to *Agni*. The cause of disease, that is, impaired metabolism can be compared with *Agnimandya*. Ayurvedic observation of hypothyroidism shows predominant *Kapha Dosha* aggravation with *Agnimandya* and *Ama* formation. Symptoms such as weight gain, lethargy, and cold intolerance support this view. Management emphasizes *Langhana*, *Deepana*, and *Pachana* therapies to restore metabolic balance. Regulation of diet and lifestyle plays a significant role. Though not directly mentioned in classical texts, hypothyroidism can be managed as *Anukta Vyadhi* based on *Dosha* involvement.

CONCLUSION

Hypothyroidism is not described in classical Ayurvedic texts. It is a condition primarily under the activity of *Agni*. Due to various *Hetus* there is aggravating *Kapha-Vata Dosha* and diminished *Agni* at *Dhatu* level. The Various systemic manifestations of the disease are due to *Dosha-Dushya* involment at various *Dhatu*s along with mainly *Rasa*, *Rakta Mansa Srotas* involment. During the treatment of Hypothyroidism all these pathogenetic factors have to be targeted. So, drugs having *Agni* along with *Dhatwagni Deepana*, *Pachana*, *Kapha Shamana*, *Vata Anulomana* and *Srotoshodhana* properties seems to be effective in this condition along with *Rasayana* and proper lifestyle as described in Ayurvedic text.

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